

Terpenoids: Part LXXXIII. Synthesis of 2-Methyl-6-methylene-2, 7-octadien-1-ol

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2-Methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-ol (I) has been prepared from 4-methylene-5-hexen-1-al (II) using the modified Wittig reaction of ethyl- α -diethyl phosphonopropionate followed by the LAH reduction of the resulting unsaturated ester in benzene.

THE acyclic monoterpene alcohol, 2-methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-ol, was isolated from essential oil of certain chemical races of *Thymus vulgaris* L. by Granger *et al.*¹ Its constitution (I) was established through chemical degradations and spectral studies.

appropriate intermediate for the synthesis of the structure (I). Preparation of this aldehyde (II) has already been reported from this lab.² earlier. However, in the present synthesis, we have prepared the aldehyde (II) following another convenient route as depicted in the Chart I.

The literature does not seem to record any attempt toward the synthesis of this terpenic alcohol. 4-Methylene-5-hexen-1-al (II) appears to be the most

appropriate intermediate for the synthesis of the structure (I). Preparation of this aldehyde (II) has already been reported from this lab.² earlier. However, in the present synthesis, we have prepared the aldehyde (II) following another convenient route as depicted in the Chart I.

Acrolein was subjected to Grignard's reaction with lithio acetal (III) (prepared by dissolving lithium in 3,3-ethylenedioxy propyl bromide³ using THF as a solvent) to afford 3-hydroxy-6,6-ethylenedioxy-1-hexene (IV). This allylic alcohol (IV) was oxidized using active MnO_2 in carbon tetrachloride to give the unsaturated ketone (V) in 70% yield. The Wittig reaction of methylene triphenylphosphorane on ketone (V) afforded 3-methylene-6,6-ethylenedioxy-1-hexene (VI) which was subsequently deketalized⁴ with PTS and aqueous acetone to give 4-methylene-

CHART I

5-hexen-1-al (II). The identity of the aldehyde (II) was confirmed by transforming it into β -myrcene (VII) through Wittig reaction².

The aldehyde (II) was reacted with ethyl- α -diethylphosphonopropionate⁵ to afford ethyl 2-methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-oate (VIII) in 63.3% yield. This α , β -unsaturated ester (VIII) was reduced with LAH in benzene⁶ to yield 2-methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-ol (I) in 80% yield. The structure of the synthetic compound was supported by its spectral data.¹

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics, using thin liquid films.

3-Hydroxy-6,6-ethylenedioxy-1-hexene (IV) :

Lithio acetal (III) was prepared by the action of 3-3-ethylenedioxy propyl bromide on lithium in THF at 10°. The 100 ml of 3.1M lithium derivative so prepared was added to acrolein (20 ml) in THF (100 ml) keeping at 0° during stirring under nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was poured into ice cold aqueous NH₄Cl solution, extracted with ether (3×40 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure to afford alcohol (IV 14.8 g; 38%); b.p. 116°–20°/10–12 mm. ν_{max} 3450, 3050, 1640, 1450, 1380, 1200, 1120, 1040, 960 and 890, cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 60.20; H, 8.74; C₈H₁₄O₃ requires : C, 60.74; H, 8.92%).

6,6-Ethylenedioxy-3-keto-1-hexene (V) :

A mixture of alcohol (IV, 10 g), carbon tetrachloride (250 ml) and active manganese dioxide (100 g) was stirred at room temperature for 6 hr. The contents were filtered and the solvent evaporated from the filtrate. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina eluting with pet ether-benzene (80 : 20). On distillation under reduced pressure it gave unsaturated ketone (V; 7 g), yield 70%: b.p. 100°–105°/7–10 mm. ν_{max} 1700, 1640, 1450, 1380, 1200, 1120, 1040, 980, 960, and 810 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 61.24; H, 7.32; C₈H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 61.52; H, 7.75%).

5,5-Ethylenedioxy-3-methylene-1-hexene (VI) :

To a solution of sodium methyl sulphanyl carbanion, prepared from sodium hydride (1 g; 50%) and DMSO (10 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere, was added a solution of methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (8.1 g) in DMSO (20 ml). The phosphorane so obtained was stirred for 15 min. Ketone (V, 2.6 g) in THF (7 ml) was added to it and stirring continued for 3 hr. and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water and extracted with pet. ether (40°–60°). The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and solvent expelled. The residue was further purified by distillation under diminished pressure to give the diene ketal (VI;

2.1 g; 84%). ν_{max} 2940, 1640, 1625, 1450, 1400, 1350, 1160, 1030, 980, 910, 890, and 810 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 69.46; H, 9.28; C₉H₁₄O₂ requires : C, 70.10; H, 9.15%).

4-Methylene-5-hexen-1-al (II) :

The ketal (VI; 2.5 g) was dissolved in acetone (85 ml) and mixed with *p*-toluena sulphonic acid (2.1 g) and water (5 ml.). This was stirred for 2.5 hr. at room temperature. The solution was diluted with ether (200 ml), washed with brine solution (60 ml) and finally dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent followed by fractionation under low pressure yielded 1.9 g (76%) of a product; b.p. 75°–82°/10–15 mm. ν_{max} 3100, 3050, 2940, 1645, 1625, 1450, 1380, 1160, 1030, 980, 960, 910, 810 and 740 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 76.15; H, 9.28; C₇H₁₀O requires : C, 76.32; H, 9.15%).

2-Methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadiene (VII) :

The aldehyde (II) was converted into β -myrcene (VII) exactly according to the procedure described in the reference 2. IR spectrum was exactly identical with that reported therein.

60 MHz NMR spectrum showed signals at: δ 1.58, 1.65 (each s, allylic methyl); δ 2.24 (d, 4H, allylic methylene); δ 5.42 (1 H, at C₃, C = CH); δ 4.9–5.2 (m, 4H, -C = CH₂); a quartet centred at δ 6.35 (1H at C₇).

2-Methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-oate (VIII) :

A slurry of sodium hydride (0.580 g; 50%) washed with *n*-hexane was placed in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) and Ethyl- α -diethyl phosphono propionate (4.1 g) was added dropwise at 20° with constant stirring until gas evolution ceased. To the resulting solution was added 4-methylene-5-hexen-1-al (II, 1.1 g) slowly at 10°; the solution was further stirred for 2 hr and kept overnight. The product was then extracted with ether (3×30 ml) after decomposing with ice cooled water. The combined ether layer was dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. The solvent was then removed and crude product after distillation under reduced pressure afforded the ester (VIII; 1.24 g) at 70°–75°/10–12 mm in 63.3% yield. ν_{max} 3090, 2950, 1725, 1640, 1620, 1450, 1390, 1330, 1270, 1020, 970, 910, 890, 810 and 740 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 74.12; H, 9.35; C₁₂H₁₈O₂; requires : C, 74.2; H, 9.3%).

Ethyl 2-methyl-6-methylene-2,7-octadien-1-ol (I) :

To a suspension of LAH (200 mg) in dry benzene (10 ml) was added slowly with stirring the ester (VIII, 1.1 g) in dry benzene (5 ml) and slurry was maintained at 50°–60° during addition. After the addition the stirring was continued for 7 hr. at 60°. The contents were cooled and decomposed in cooled saturated solution of sodium potassium tartrate. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether (4×20 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed and crude product on distillation under reduced pressure furnished alcohol (I,

0.620 g) at 75°-80°/10-12 mm in 79.9% yield. ν_{max} 3330 (broad), 3095, 3010, 2900, 1670, 1640, 1620, 1450, 1390, 1030, 1000, 990, 910, 890, 810 and 740 cm^{-1} .

60 MHz NMR spectrum showed signals at δ 2.22 (d, 4H, allylic methylene); δ 1.77 (s, 3H, allylic methyl); δ 4.05 (s, 2H at C₁); δ 1.95 (1H, of -OH); δ 5.34 (1H at C₃); δ 4.88-5.3 (4H, -C = CH₂); δ 6.36 (q, 1H at C₇). (Found : C, 78.84; H, 10.70; C₁₀H₁₆O requires : C, 78.88; H, 10.5%).

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